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Student Masters Level

MINIMUM VIABLE SKILLS PROFILE

Student Masters Level

Minimum Viable Skills Profile

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Disclaimer

This booklet is part of the **Skills4EOSC collection of Minimum Viable Skills Profiles (MVS)**, which outline key Open Science competencies for different professional roles. It presents a focused extract from the **Annex to Deliverable D2.6**, designed to support usability and communication. To explore the full list of profiles, visit the Skills4EOSC website (<https://www.skills4eosoc.eu/resources/publications/mvs>) or consult the full Annex (<https://zenodo.org/records/15761916>).

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics	MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement	ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
DMP	Data Management Plan	OS	Open Science
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues	R&I	Research and Innovation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	RDA	Research Data Alliance
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)	RDM	Research Data Management
ICT	Information and Communication Technology	RI	Research Infrastructure
IT	Information Technology	RPO	Research Performing Organisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre	RSE	Research Software Engineer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

1. Introduction

Open Science mission for this role

The **Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Masters Level** is one of two MVS for students (the other for undergraduate students). As Masters level education is **more specialised and focused than the undergraduate level this MVS considers the skills and competencies in Open Science (OS)** needed for more focused study, incorporating OS into their project workflows. This is a generic profile for students in postgraduate education.

For information related to basic skills for researchers, see the MVS designed specifically for Early Career Researchers, which addresses the minimum skills and competencies needed for PhD student and post-doctoral researchers.

It is recognised that Open Science skills should be immersed within formal education at its earliest stages. By engaging with Open Science **practices and acquiring relevant knowledge of OS** early in their careers, the benefits of these practices can be recognised, even if their careers are not in academia.

STUDENT - MASTERS LEVEL

ORGANISATIONAL CONTEXT:

- Research Performing Organizations

ESSENTIAL SKILLS FOR THIS ROLE

- Ability to analyse OS and FAIR concepts and ideas in the respective field of study. Where relevant, includes knowledge of ways to share and produce FAIR research data, code and software, and of how to use data repositories.
- Intermediate digital research skills, data management, data communication. Includes demonstrating an understanding of the research life cycle, including planning, design, analysis, publication, and dissemination. Includes the ability to organise project workflow using file folders, document naming conventions, version control, cloud storage (etc.).
- Ability to obtain open science knowledge and apply FAIR principles, including relevant discipline or domain-specific information. Includes performing literature and data searches efficiently: finding and reusing open scientific papers, as well as finding, understanding, (re)using, and analysing the appropriate data types and formats for assignments.
- Open publication literacy skills, including knowledge of how to navigate open access sources and open access publication models applied to OA repositories.
- Basic understanding of the relevant legal issues related to Open Science practices, including Intellectual Property Rights, copyright-related issues like Open Access, Open Licensing, using and citing third-parties works. Also includes Non-Personal Data e.g., being aware of rules on the use of “research data”.
- Knowledge of how to apply data protection requirements together with Open Science/FAIR principles. Includes Personal Data Protection and Governance e.g., using Personal Data under the current legal framework, and following Data Protection policies.
- General understanding of ethical principles e.g. transparency, diversity and accountability; and best practices e.g. avoiding bias in data processing when using data-driven technologies. Includes ability to relate these principles to their field of expertise, by applying the general ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct, e.g. the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

SOFT / TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

Considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration skills, ability to engage in teamwork. • Assignment and/or dissertation management. • Organizational skills, including goal setting, time management, and prioritizing. • Verbal communication and interpersonal skills. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Written communication. • Problem solving. • Critical thinking. • Presentation skills. |
|---|--|

BACKGROUND ASSUMPTIONS

MAIN ACTIVITIES

Engages with OS outputs, and contributes to data literacy activities that improve their understanding of the concepts and principles of Open Science, including:

- | | |
|--|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interpreting and critically evaluating data. • Finding, selecting, accessing, and creating data sets. • Ethically using and citing data. • Understanding basic data types and formats. • Communicating data with visualizations. • Understanding how data is collected. • Manipulating data from different sources, formats, and structures. • Understanding how to store and share data. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding why it is important to manage data. • Plans, organises, and manages assignments related to dissertations. Specific activities related to OS include: • Using a data management plan to describe efforts to make research reproducible, including providing descriptions of the data via metadata, research procedures and analyses. • Writing manuscripts and/or dissertations transparently, sharing hypotheses and justifying decisions, and sharing methodologies. • Sharing any data used for projects, making the data available for researchers. |
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CONTRIBUTES TO WHICH OPEN SCIENCE OUTCOMES?

Non-research graduate students contribute to the following Open Science outcomes:

- The adoption and practice of OS and FAIR principles and methods.
- Increasing transparency and knowledge sharing in research processes.
- Increasing knowledge and awareness of digital literacy.

Further information

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS TERMS

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Perform project management](#); [Manage research data](#); [Synthesize research publications](#); [Manage open publications](#); [Manage findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable data](#); [Operate open source software](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Plan](#); [Conduct web searches](#); [Apply knowledge of science, technology, and engineering](#); [Work in teams](#); [Address an audience](#); [Moderate a discussion](#); [Report facts](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Manage time](#); [Organise information, objects, and resources](#); [Solve problems](#); [Critically evaluate information and its sources](#); [Think critically](#); [Show initiative](#); [Assume responsibility](#); [Show confidence](#).

ResearchComp: [Manage research data](#); [Apply research ethics and integrity principles](#); [Problem solving](#); [Creativity](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data transformation](#); [Data validation and cleaning](#); [Open access publishing](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Research governance](#); [Data policy](#).

CSCCE: [Data analysis](#); [Data visualization](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Time management](#).

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